

Peer Corrective Feedback Practices and Perceptions among Chinese Learners of English

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ABSTRACT

Peer interaction and peer corrective feedback (PCF) have been continuing interest to both practitioners and researchers. Empirical studies in various contexts have shown that factors like proficiency levels and communication styles can impact peer interaction and the provision of PCF (e.g., Choi & Iwashita, 2016; Nguyen & Newton, 2020). However, existing studies on Chinese learners have largely focused on their attitudes toward PCF. To fill this gap, this study explores Chinese learners' practices and perceptions regarding how their perceived proficiency level and communication style affect PCF. Twenty-seven Chinese international students at an Australian university were assigned three proficiency groups based on the pre-task proficiency assessment. They completed group interaction tasks with participants of different and similar proficiency. Recorded and transcribed group interactions were coded for language-related episodes (LREs) and PCF. Quantitative analysis showed no significant effect of proficiency level on the number of LREs and PCF. Post-task interviews revealed that Chinese learners mostly had positive feelings about PCF. However, some hesitation was noted, which was linked to the learners' perceived proficiency levels. Learners used indirect and inclusive language to soften negative comments. This study highlights how proficiency levels, communication styles, and learner perceptions affect PCF.

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Understanding these factors can help educators improve teaching methods and create more effective collaborative learning environments for Chinese learners.

Keywords: Chinese English learners, communication style, learner perception, peer corrective feedback, peer interaction, proficiency level

INTRODUCTION

Corrective feedback (CF) refers to the responses elicited by learners' erroneous production of their second language (L2) (Li, 2010). CF can be provided in written and oral forms. Oral CF may originate from various sources, including teachers, native speakers, and peers. When a peer with equivalent status as a learner delivers CF, it is commonly termed peer corrective feedback (PCF). PCF plays a crucial role in fostering language learning as reported in empirical studies: development in language acquisition, including grammar acquisition (Kim, 2013; Sippel & Jackson, 2015), vocabulary (Sippel, 2019), and pronunciation (Martin & Sippel, 2021).

While PCF has received continuing attention (Iwashita & Dao, 2021), it remains relatively less explored than teacher CF (Sato, 2017). A large volume of the CF research in the context of Chinese learners has concentrated on teacher feedback (e.g., Chu, 2011; Zhai & Gao, 2018), leaving a notable gap in understanding PCF in this context. Studies conducted in a non-Chinese context showed that factors such as proficiency level (Choi & Iwashita, 2016; Nguyen & Newton, 2020), learners' perceptions of their peers' proficiency levels (Kim, 2020; Watanabe & Swain, 2008), and communication style (Carson & Nelson, 1996; Yan, 2016) can influence the quality and quantity of peer interaction and PCF. There is limited research on how proficiency levels and communication styles affect peer corrective feedback (PCF) among Chinese learners. In Chinese cultural contexts, providing feedback can be seen as a face-threatening act (Ergül, 2021), leading to less frequent PCF in group settings. Chinese communication is often indirect, with a reluctance to criticise (Carson & Nelson, 1996), although learners can be more direct with friends (Yan, 2016). Additionally, collaborative learning activities are less common in China (e.g., Li et al., 2014), potentially making students less inclined to engage in PCF.

This study aimed to fill the current research gap by exploring how communication style, proficiency level, and learner perception influence PCF among Chinese learners. It provides insights into the characteristics of Chinese language learners'

PCF and their perceptions of PCF, revealing how communication style may affect group work dynamics, yielding useful information about implementing group work in teaching Chinese learners and designing effective PCF training for Chinese students.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Peer Interaction and PCF

PCF occurs within interactions among L2-L2 speakers (peer interaction). Peer interaction provides a context that offers richer learning prospects than interactions involving first language (L1) and L2 speakers (Sato, 2017). The richer learning opportunities from peer interaction can be explained through sociocultural perspectives (Nassaji & Swain, 2000). The sociocultural perspective argues that knowledge is built through social interactions, such as collaboration and learner communication (Vygotsky & Cole, 1978). According to this perspective, learning is viewed as an embedded process during interaction and it happens within the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), which is the gap between what learners can do independently and what they can achieve with help from adults or more capable peers (Nassaji & Swain, 2000). Scaffolding, another concept proposed by sociocultural theories, refers to a situation where a knowledgeable person provides support that helps learners build their skills and knowledge to a higher level. During group work, L2 learners participate in collaborative dialogue, or the cooperative creation of language by two or more people (Swain, 1997) and mutually support each other's learning. They need scaffolding within their ZPD as they interact with the teacher or peers (Nassaji & Swain, 2000). Providing and receiving corrective feedback can be seen as scaffolding where learners engage and exchange meaningful information with their peers in their ZPD (Nassaji & Swain, 2000). Therefore, PCF serves as a mediating tool that guides learners in language learning, supporting them in understanding and constructing meaning within social learning environments. When examining the dynamics of peer interaction, PCF possesses distinctive characteristics wherein L2 learners assume dual roles as providers and receivers of PCF, as outlined in the dual model proposed by Sato (2017). Sato (2017) posits that social and affective factors among peers may impact peer interaction. Therefore, understanding the nuances of these interactions is crucial, as a collaboratively constructed relationship with peers may significantly influence learning outcomes more than other factors, such as proficiency level (Watanabe, 2008).

Empirical Studies on PCF

Empirical studies suggest that teacher feedback is more likely to be adopted in contexts where teachers hold greater authority (e.g., Miao et al., 2006; Zhao, 2010). When providing PCF, learners may be reluctant to correct their peers' errors due to their proficiency levels and social concerns, including the fear of being perceived as arrogant (Philp et al., 2010). The effectiveness of PCF can be enhanced when students receive proper training. The benefits of peer feedback are amplified when students are prepared for the skills and demonstrate a willingness to engage in PCF (e.g., Han & Xu, 2019; Pitt et al., 2019).

Researchers have examined the benefits of PCF after training for the development of linguistic forms (e.g., question formation in Kim (2013); accuracy and fluency in Sato and Lyster (2012); present perfect tense verbs in Sippel and Jackson (2015); vocabulary items in Sippel (2019) and pronunciation in Martin & Sippel (2021). For example, Kim (2013) found that L1 Korean EFL learners who viewed the instructional videos detailing correction strategies before language tasks improved their ability to formulate L2 questions compared to the control group participants. Similarly, Sato and Lyster (2012) found that, at a Japanese university, students trained in delivering prompts and recasts exhibited superior accuracy and fluency development compared to both the peer-interaction-only and the control group.

Sippel and colleagues conducted several studies investigating the effect of PCF on various aspects of performance in the German language. Sippel and Jackson (2015) compared the effectiveness of oral CF from teachers and peers in acquiring German present perfect tense. The study revealed that while both teacher and peer feedback groups were beneficial, the peer feedback group demonstrated superior long-term gains and engaged in more frequent self-correction and discussions concerning linguistic forms. Building on this, Sippel (2019) examined the efficacy of PCF in form-focused instruction (FFI), a style of teaching where students are guided to make connections between language forms and a meaning-focused context (Sippel, 2019). The study revealed that participants who received CF training showed a significant advantage in vocabulary development over the other experimental groups. Furthermore, Martin and Sippel (2021) found that providing PCF was more beneficial for pronunciation development than receiving it.

These studies highlight the benefits of incorporating PCF training into language teaching and learning. However, studies have also reported individual factors' influence on PCF (e.g., Philp et al., 2010). Therefore, it is important to understand

how individual factors such as proficiency level, communication style and learner perception can influence PCF.

Impact of Individual Factors on Peer Interaction

Studies have extensively examined peer interaction by analysing language-related episodes (LREs), defined as instances where learners reflect on or question their language usage (e.g., Swain & Lapkin, 1998). Various factors moderate types and amount of LREs during peer interaction, including learners' proficiency levels, perceptions of their peers' proficiency, and communication styles (Carson & Nelson, 1996; Choi & Iwashita, 2016; Kim, 2020; Nguyen & Newton, 2020; Tian & Li, 2018; Watanabe, 2008; Watanabe & Swain, 2008; Yan, 2016).

Proficiency Level

Both objectively assessed and perceived proficiency levels can shape the dynamics and outcomes of peer interaction during collaborative language tasks. For instance, Watanabe (2008) examined the impact of pairing three learners of varying proficiency levels, i.e., higher or lower, during collaborative tasks and found that proficiency differences did not decisively affect the frequency of LREs or the quality of collaborative work measured by each member's contribution and participation. Similarly, focusing on low-proficiency learners, Choi and Iwashita (2016) investigated whether the proficiency level of group members may impact the occurrence of LREs and reported on the impact of proficiency levels on the frequency of LREs. The findings revealed that low-proficiency learners were less inclined to engage in LREs when grouped with peers of similar (low) proficiency, leading to more unresolved and incorrectly resolved LREs. They were also less likely to receive beneficial assistance from peers of low proficiency. In contrast, Nguyen and Newton (2020) found that low-proficiency dyads in a Vietnamese EFL context generated a significantly greater number of LREs compared to their high-proficiency counterparts, possibly due to the nature of the oral open-ended tasks that potentially heightened participants' awareness of language deficiencies (Nguyen & Newton, 2020).

Subjectively perceived proficiency levels also influence peer interaction. Watanabe and Swain (2008) suggest that Japanese English as a second language (ESL) learners' perceptions of their peers' proficiency levels may wield a more substantial influence on the nature of peer assistance than objectively measured proficiency levels. Similarly, Kim (2020) found that Korean EFL learners' perceptions of their peers' abilities could affect their willingness to engage in

collaborative tasks. Some participants felt motivated when paired with peers with higher-perceived proficiency, while others experienced frustration and embarrassment. In addition to the perception of peers' proficiency level, Philp et al. (2010) found learners' reticence to correct peers' errors due to their proficiency level. However, there remains a dearth of research examining how learners' perceptions of their proficiency levels affect peer interaction.

Communication Style

Another significant factor potentially impacting peer interaction is participants' communication style, the way one communicates and interacts with others (Norton, 1978). Culture profoundly influences communication styles, as highlighted by Carson and Nelson (1996), who posit that individuals from collectivist cultures, like Chinese, typically prioritise group harmony and mutual face-saving in collaborative settings. In Carson and Nelson (1996), the interaction patterns of three Chinese ESL learners engaging with peers from diverse cultural backgrounds were analysed. The findings revealed a reluctance among the Chinese participants to express disagreement or claim authority, often employing strategies such as under-specification and indirection to mitigate criticism or negative feedback. Similarly, Tian and Li (2018) reported Chinese learners' tendency to use euphemistic language, indirectness, under-specification, and offering excuses for errors to mitigate the impact of negative feedback. This phenomenon of culturally impacted communication styles is not limited to Chinese culture. For example, Finnish and Japanese communication styles are described as quiet and introverted, contrasting with the extroverted and talkative Indian communication style (Nishimura et al., 2008). Social status also influences communication style. Yan (2016) found that Chinese students exhibit a heightened sensitivity to social power dynamics. Specifically, students use more polite, indirect strategies when disagreeing with higher-status individuals but are more direct with peers of equal status.

Learner Perceptions of PCF

Apart from learner proficiency and communication style, learner perception of PCF has been identified as a factor influencing the provision of PCF (Sato, 2017). While some studies report learners' positive attitudes toward PCF (Sippel, 2020), others indicate a preference for teacher CF (Mahvelati, 2021; Schulz, 2001). Regarding Chinese learners' perceptions of PCF, Zhu and Wang (2019) surveyed 2670 Chinese undergraduate students regarding their attitudes toward PCF through a

questionnaire. Their findings indicated generally positive attitudes toward PCF among Chinese learners. However, participants preferred less frequent PCF than teacher feedback. Furthermore, Xu et al. (2019) observed that more PCF was directed towards morphological and syntactical errors. PCF was found to be influenced by social dynamics; positive peer relationships could either encourage or deter the provision of PCF. Xu et al. (2019) noted that close friendships might mitigate concerns of face-threatening situations arising from correction, yet familiarity between peers could lead to overlooking errors.

The existing research has largely focused on non-Chinese learners, examining how communication styles and proficiency levels—both objectively measured and subjectively perceived—affect peer interaction. However, there is a limited exploration into how these factors influence peer interaction and PCF among Chinese learners of English. Considering the unique context where many Chinese ESL learners in Australia learn English, few group activities and PCF are seen as face-threatening, it is unclear how the findings of the studies conducted in a non-Chinese context could apply to Chinese learners. To fill these gaps, the current study aims to examine learners' practices and perceptions of peer interaction and PCF by addressing the following research questions (RQ):

1. What linguistic features characterise peer interaction in different proficiency groups of Chinese English learners?
2. To what extent does Chinese English learners' perceived proficiency level influence the provision and reception of PCF during peer interaction?
3. To what extent does Chinese English learners' communication style affect their PCF during peer interaction?

METHODOLOGY

This study is part of a large project investigating various factors that impact peer interaction among learners from various language backgrounds. This manuscript focused on Chinese students only, exploring their interaction patterns regarding the occurrence of LREs and PCF and the possible influence of proficiency and communication styles on their interaction. A mixed method design based on Choi and Iwashita (2016) and Spinelli (2024) was employed, including group activities with collaborative writing tasks followed by a semi-structured focused group interview. The overall design is shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Data collection procedure

Participants

Twenty-seven Chinese international students (Female=22, Male=5) enrolled full-time at a large urban university in Australia participated in the study. They were pursuing various bachelor or postgraduate degrees (e.g., Bachelor of Commerce, Master of Business, etc.) at the time of data collection. All participants, aged 21-30, were from Mainland China, spoke Mandarin as their first language, and had lived in Australia for an average of 2.2 years. They had studied English for over 12 years and were at B1 to C1 proficiency levels according to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). Participants were recruited through WeChat (a social application) campus activity groups.

Assessment of Participants' Proficiency

All participants completed the Structure and Written Expression section of an institutional TOEFL (TOEFL, 1994), with scores converted to CEFR levels. Additionally, they completed a CEFR self-assessment sheet to evaluate their perception of their language proficiency regarding listening, reading, spoken interaction, spoken production and writing. Based on their test scores and self-assessments, participants were divided into low-proficiency ($N=16$) and high-proficiency ($N=11$).

Tasks and Group Assignment

The task comprised four parts (Figure 1). First, a warm-up activity had participants recall group work experiences, followed by viewing a two-minute clip from *Toy Story 3*. Participants then engaged in a five-minute speaking activity, answering one fixed question about the scene and one open-ended question about potential subsequent events. Next, they spent 10 minutes crafting a creative conclusion, with three minutes for revision. Participants were encouraged to interact in English but could use their first language if needed.

To understand how proficiency level affects group dynamics, participants were assigned to three proficiency groups (high-dominant, low, and mixed) based on TOEFL and CEFR self-assessments. Participants worked with peers with different or similar proficiency levels. The high-dominant group had one low-proficiency participant with the rest being high-proficient. The low group comprised only low-proficiency learners, and the mixed group included both. This grouping followed Choi and Iwashita's (2016) study. Most participants engaged with two to three proficiency groups, with group sizes of three to five members.

Participants completed an opinion gap task with three versions (A, B and C). Opinion gap tasks require learners to articulate their preferences or attitudes as part of task completion (Prabhu, 1987), thus promoting negotiation (Ellis, 2003). The order of participation was counterbalanced, e.g., some participants did task A in a mixed proficiency group, others did A in a high-dominant group. Detailed group assignments are in Appendix A.

Interviews

After group activities, five low-proficiency B1 participants (three females, two males) participated in semi-structured focus group interviews. They were selected

to complete all three versions and interact with peers of varying proficiency levels. Divided into two groups, they discussed their perspectives on group activities, proficiency levels, communication styles, and PCF. Questions were asked in English and Chinese, allowing participants to express themselves comfortably, covering tasks, proficiency levels, communication styles, and PCF (Appendix B).

Data Collection

The data collection procedure lasted over three weeks (see Figure 1). In the first week, a pilot study with three Chinese international students (two high- and one low-proficiency learners) tested task timing and interview questions, leading to edits based on their feedback. Participant recruitment and proficiency assessment were undertaken in the second week. In the third week, participants' self-assessment, group interactions and interviews were administered on the same day.

Data Analysis

The audio-recorded group interactions and interviews were transcribed verbatim. Transcripts include 12 group interactions (288 minutes) and two interviews (96 minutes), covering all activities: video, discussion and writing. Only the discussion and writing portions were analysed. The analysis involved all participants to get a broad picture of group dynamics across the groups unlike previous studies (Choi & Iwashita, 2016; Spinelli, 2024) which focused only low proficiency learners.

Language-Related Episodes (LREs)

The transcripts of each group activity were coded with the grammatical and lexical LREs. The number was manually counted. Lexical LREs occur when learners discuss the meaning, spelling and/or pronunciation of vocabulary. Example 1 shows a lexical LRE from a low-proficiency group.

Example 1

1. LP1 (22:14): purchase怎么拼啊? P-O-R-S-H-E-S? <How do you spell 'purchase'? P-O-R-S-H-E-S? >
2. LP4 (22:17): 买。 <To buy.> Purchase. P-U-R-C-H-A-S-E.
3. (Low proficiency group 2)

Grammatical LREs indicate learners discussing the syntactical and/or morphological aspects. In Example 2, participants discussed the past tense of “catch”.

Example 2

1. HP1 (09:40): 好奇怪啊caught。 <Caught is so weird.>
2. LP1 (09:43): 是caught up吧。 Caught up。 <It's caught up, right? Caught up.>
3. HP1 (09:44): Caught.

(Mixed proficiency group 2)

Peer Corrective Feedback (PCF)

The transcripts of group tasks were also analysed for PCF, employing the coding categories used in Lyster and Ranta (1997). Example 3 shows a PCF episode of repetition and elicitation, where HP1 first repeated LP2's utterance and then elicit LP2 to self-correct.

Example 3

1. LP1 (21:16): Je-Jessie gra-grabbed their friends one by one use, use the their...
2. LP2 (21:32): Jessie grabs.
3. HP1 (21:33): Grabs? Grabs or grabbed?
4. LP2 (21:36): uh, 有ed的。 <Uh, with an ed.>

(Mixed proficiency group 2)

The intercoder reliability is ensured by having a second coder to code 20% of the data. In case of discrepancy, the coders discussed each discrepant item to understand the reason behind their different choices and reached a consensus on the correct coding. After the coding, the frequency of LREs and PCF was calculated to answer research question 1.

Interviews

The interview data was transcribed, translated, and analysed for themes related to proficiency level, communication style, and PCF. Responses on perceived proficiency and its impact on PCF were analysed to address research question 2. Data from sections three and four were examined to answer research question 3 regarding communication style. To maintain anonymity, each interviewee was referred to by a pseudonym in the subsequent analysis.

RESULTS

This study examined peer interactions among Chinese learners, analysing factors that influence PCF through a mixed-method approach. This section presents findings from both quantitative and qualitative analyses in relation to the research questions.

Linguistic Characteristics of Peer Interaction (RQ1)

Language-related Episodes (LREs)

Table 1 summarises the LREs produced by twelve groups (27 participants): five low-proficiency groups, four mixed-proficiency groups, and three high-dominant groups. Participants produced 87 grammatical LREs and 88 lexical LREs during group interaction tasks. The high-dominant groups generated most grammatical LREs, while low-proficiency groups led in lexical LREs. Notably, lexical LREs variation among groups was minimal, as shown in small SDs.

Table 1. LRE Occurrences by proficiency groups

	Low (<i>n</i> =5)	Mixed (<i>n</i> =4)	High-dominant (<i>n</i> =3)	Total (<i>n</i> =12)
Grammatical				
Total	36	24	27	87
<i>M</i>	7.2	6	9	7.25
<i>SD</i>	1.83	1.41	5.1	3.14
Lexical				
Total	40	28	20	88
<i>M</i>	8	7	6.67	7.33
<i>SD</i>	3.03	3.16	1.69	2.86

Notes: *n* denotes the number of groups.

Lexical LREs consistently appeared across tasks, mainly focusing on spelling and word choice, while grammatical LREs were more frequent during the final task phase when participants revised their work. Nearly all groups engaged in LREs concerning tense discussions, occurring most frequently within the low-proficiency groups, characterised by extended length, uncertainty, and incorrect resolution. In mixed-proficiency groups, high-dominant group participants provided brief corrections, while high-dominant groups offered detailed explanations, such as justifying past tense. Conversely, low- and mixed-proficiency groups rarely provided such explanations.

Peer Corrective Feedback (PCF)

Table 2 provides a summary of the PCF generated by 12 groups. 63 PCF were produced in total. Mixed-proficiency groups produced the highest average frequency of PCF production, while the lowest frequency of PCF was observed among the high-dominant group.

Table 2. PCF Occurrences by proficiency groups

	Low ($n=5$)	Mixed ($n=4$)	High-dominant ($n=3$)	Total ($n=12$)
Total	26	23	14	63
<i>M</i>	5.2	5.75	4.67	5.25
<i>SD</i>	3.06	3.11	1.24	2.77

Notes: n denotes the number of groups.

Table 3 displays the categories of PCF and their mean occurrences across three proficiency groups. Recast and explicit correction were the most common PCF types, whereas clarification requests and elicitation were the least used. Recast dominated within low-proficiency participants, while explicit correction was most frequent within mixed-proficiency groups. Figure 2 shows the distribution of PCF types and frequency by group. The low-proficiency groups used four types, mixed-proficiency groups five, and high-dominant groups three.

Table 3. PCF types by proficiency groups

	Low ($n=5$)	Mixed ($n=4$)	High-dominant ($n=3$)	Total ($n=12$)
Explicit correction	6	9	4	19
<i>M</i>	1.2	2.25	1.33	1.58
Recast	17	10	6	32
<i>M</i>	3.4	2.5	2	2.66
Clarification request	1	0	0	1
<i>M</i>	0.2	0	0	0.08

Notes: n denotes the number of groups.

Table 4. *PCF types by proficiency groups (continued)*

	Low (<i>n</i> =5)	Mixed (<i>n</i> =4)	High-dominant (<i>n</i> =3)	Total (<i>n</i> =12)
Metalinguistic feedback	0	2	2	4
<i>M</i>	0	0.5	0.67	0.33
Elicitation	0	2	0	2
<i>M</i>	0	0.5	0	0.16
Repetition	2	1	2	5
<i>M</i>	0.4	0.25	0.67	0.42

Examination of interaction data reveals how PCF was delivered. For example, recast was employed to address grammatical errors and inappropriate word choice, such as when a low-proficiency participant incorrectly utilised the present tense for a past event. It also addressed incorrect vocabulary choices and encompasses translations in response to the use of native language (Lyster & Ranta, 1997). Since L1 was not restricted, participants were found translating their peers' native language (Mandarin Chinese). Explicit correction involves providing the correct form (Lyster & Ranta, 1997). It was most commonly used during the final phase of the task, when participants reviewed their writings, to correct inaccurate use of grammatical and lexical items.

Proficiency Level and PCF (RQ2)

To answer the research question 2 regarding how perceived proficiency level influences PCF, two focus-group interviews were analysed. Four themes were identified: their low perceived proficiency level, preference for working with higher-proficiency peers, and how perceived proficiency level influences provision and reception of PCF.

Figure 2. PCF types and numbers in each group

Notes: “High” refers to high-dominant groups.

Low Perceived Proficiency Level

As explained above, before task activities, participants completed a CEFR self-assessment sheet investigating their subjectively perceived proficiency level. According to the self-assessment sheets, all five participants interviewed perceived their proficiency levels to be within the B1 to B2 range. Participants perceived proficiency levels to be lower than their TOEFL-assessed levels. The post-task focus group interviews elicited participants’ perspectives regarding their subjectively perceived proficiency and how they believed their proficiency level might influence their behaviour during group work.

When asked about their perception of their language proficiency level, the descriptor employed most frequently in the interviews was “average.” Ling

expressed having “difficulty reading,” while Jia thought that, despite considering herself average, it was more crucial that one “dare to speak.”

Preference for working with higher proficiency peers

When queried about collaborating with peers, participants preferred study groups with mixed proficiencies, while some expressed concern regarding wide proficiency gaps. Most favoured working with higher-proficiency peers. Ling noted that she “might ask more questions” to learn from higher-proficiency peers and would take on a leadership role when working with lower-proficiency peers. Jia posited that high-proficiency peers motivated her to communicate in English and be mindful of her accent and language use. Ling also stated that she would “mimic” more proficient peers. However, Zhen noted that he would not modify his style when working with learners of varying proficiencies due to his proficiency limitations.

Provision and Reception of PCF

Participants articulated concerns about how proficiency level affects their provision of PCF, including difficulties identifying errors, comprehending others’ PCF, and the potential to offend others. Jia indicated that she sometimes struggled to recognize mistakes, while Lan worried about offending when correcting them in English. Regarding the impact of peers’ proficiency levels on PCF reception, interviewees generally exhibited a humble attitude, asserting that there would be “no big difference,” as shown in Excerpt 1. Their practices evidenced this stance; they expressed no dissatisfaction with PCF, and their discussions were harmonious. Lan and Yun agreed that their language ability could hinder their understanding of PCF.

Excerpt 1

RA: Do you feel the same corrected by people with higher and lower level than you?

Zhen: Nothing different.

Ling: No big difference. If I am wrong, I’m wrong. The level doesn’t matter. I am wrong.

Communication Style and PCF (RQ3)

To answer the research question 3 regarding how Chinese learners' communication style influences their PCF, two focus-group interviews and interaction data were analysed. Three themes were identified: confidence in native language and concerns about miscommunication in English, communication style, and how communication style affected their PCF practices.

Confidence in Native Language and Concerns About Miscommunication in English

Participants felt more confident speaking Chinese than English, due to its natural fluency and lack of fear of mistakes. They thought they could be more "precise," "deep," and speak faster using Chinese (Excerpt 2). While in English, they often found their minds struggling to keep up with their speech, leading to mistakes and misunderstandings.

Excerpt 2

Lan: One difference is limited English proficiency. In Chinese, I can delve deeper into topics, but in English, my points are simplistic due to language limitations.

Yun: I think it's about detail. In Chinese, I can be more precise, but in English, there might be misunderstandings due to less precise word choice.

Chinese Communication Style

All five interviewees agreed that Chinese or Japanese people tend to be more indirect in communication than Westerners. Lan and Zhen attributed this to cultural factors, with Lan noting that direct disagreement in East Asian contexts could make others feel "uncomfortable." Most participants were reluctant or hesitant to voice disagreement, preferring to express it indirectly and "gently." The way they expressed disagreement depended on the interlocutors and the conversation goals (Excerpt 3).

Excerpt 3

Lan: Then, I would consider whether we have a common goal that needs to be achieved. ... If it's relevant to me, I would remind them, but in a gentle way. If there's no particular goal, then I wouldn't really bother.

Ling: I think it depends on the person, if I meet that kind of foreign group member, then I can be very direct with him and say I think I don't quite agree with your point of view, and then what do I think. If it's a Chinese participant, I may have to be a bit more euphemistic.

Communication Style and PCF

When questioned about providing PCF in group tasks, the interviewees emphasised factors similar to those involved in handling disagreement, that their approach to delivering PCF would vary depending on the significance of the task and whether peers in the group use direct or indirect communication style (Excerpt 4).

Excerpt 4

Lan: Sometimes I tend to adapt to the environment first. For example, if everyone in the group tends to express their opinions directly and point out mistakes straightforwardly, then when I speak English, I'll definitely do the same. However, if I'm new to this environment, I might still follow the patterns of my native language, even when speaking English.

All interviewees were generally open to receiving PCF and concurred that they would only offer it frequently if it impacted the conversation outcome. They reported limited experiences of feeling hurt by or causing hurt through PCF but acknowledged that insults or unfriendly or commanding tone could be offensive. Most agreed that they would deliver PCF gently and indirectly. Despite using implicit corrections, participants applied several strategies to soften their PCF. They used strategies like rising tones or question forms to soften their feedback, as shown in Excerpts 5 and 6.

Excerpt 5

- 1 HP2: =应该是, 对 <Yeah, it maybe, right> sorry, then he come come come came up, with the idea that he could make some noise and distract, Andy's mom, so he pull the sound ring **and talked**((Writing)), 可以吗? <Okay?>=
- 2 HP4: =**talked to?**=
- 3 HP3: =就是talked((laugh)) <Just talked is ok((laugh))>

(High-dominant group 1)

Excerpt 6

- 1 LP1 (19:59): 这里是不是应该是thought过去= < *Shouldn't this be the 'thought' past tense*>

(Low proficiency group 3)

When giving explicit correction, learners might use inclusive language, such as “It’s better to say,” framing the correction as a suggestion and making it more collaborative (Excerpt 7). Another strategy was to convey humility and reduce authority using tentative language such as “I may not be right” (Excerpt 8).

Excerpt 7

- 1 LP3: = **Without Woody who want to be free, work together**
- 2 HP1(22:22): 有一个是except Woody好一些, all the toys except Woody<*It's better to say except Woody, all the toys except Woody*>=
- 3 LP3: =**except**=

(Mixed proficiency group 1)

Excerpt 8

1. LP2 (20:21): 这里加ed, started吧, 我也不一定是对的。< Add ed here, 'started', I may not be right.>

(Mixed proficiency group 3)

DISCUSSION

The present study investigated how proficiency level and communication style affect Chinese English language learners’ practices and perceptions of peer interaction and PCF. In this chapter, the findings are interpreted by referring to the previous research and organised according to the research questions.

Linguistic Features of Peer Interaction in Different Proficiency Groups (RQ1)

The results indicate varying characteristics in LREs and PCF across proficiency groups. Descriptive statistics indicate that high-dominant groups produced the most grammatical LREs, while low-proficiency groups generated the most lexical LREs. However, the disparity in LREs among groups was minimal, contrasting with Watanabe's (2008) findings where some participants generated significantly fewer LREs with lower-proficiency peers. In this study, all groups collaborated equally, with each member contributing ideas, writing parts of the composition and checking grammar. This collaboration reflects Swain's (1997) notion of collaborative dialogue, where learners co-construct knowledge and share linguistic problem-solving, regardless of individual proficiency differences.

In terms of PCF, mixed-proficiency groups exhibited the most frequent PCF episodes. From sociocultural perspectives, proficiency differences create opportunities for scaffolding, as higher-proficiency learners provide feedback and explanations, while lower-proficiency learners benefit from the PCF within their ZPD. Recast was the most frequently used strategy, consistent with Xu et al. (2019), who found that Chinese students preferred recast over other correction strategies. However, unlike Xu et al. (2019), where explicit correction was the least frequent, this study found it to be the second most common strategy, surpassing clarification request, metalinguistic feedback, elicitation and repetition. The difference may be due to the writing revision phase in this study, where participants were reminded to check their grammar and vocabulary, leading to a higher frequency of explicit corrections during the final review.

Influence of Perceived Proficiency Level on PCF (RQ2)

Interview findings suggest that learner perceptions of their proficiency levels can influence both the provision and reception of PCF during peer interaction. Generally, participants preferred working with higher-proficiency peers for more learning opportunities. With lower-proficiency peers, participants often assumed a leadership role, aligning with Kim (2020), who found that participants felt greater responsibility and positioned themselves as experts to support and guide their partners. Concerns about identifying others' mistakes due to low perceived proficiency correspond with Xu et al. (2019), where a lack of knowledge was the most cited discouraging factor in providing CF. Participants generally held a positive attitude toward receiving PCF, consistent with Zhu and Wang (2019). However, Zhu and Wang (2019) did not specify the proficiency level of peers

providing PCF. Participants showed a humble attitude towards PCF regardless of their peers' proficiency level but expressed concerns about their proficiency level when understanding PCF. These concerns highlight the variability in learners' ZPD, as PCF may not always align with their current linguistic capabilities. According to Nassaji and Swain (2000), effective scaffolding occurs when feedback is negotiated within the learner's ZPD, suggesting that students may benefit from training in collaborative negotiation to better scaffold each other's learning.

Impact of Communication Style on PCF (RQ3)

While the collectivist cultural background of Chinese learners (Carson & Nelson, 1996) may encourage the collaborative behaviours in group work in this study, as group harmony and mutual assistance are highly valued, peer interaction may also be further complicated by the indirect communication style of Chinese learners. Participants agreed that they have a more indirect communication style compared to Westerners, whom they considered blunter and more direct. Factors such as interlocutors' and peers' communication styles affected how they expressed opinions and gave PCF. Participants indicated that they would be direct with non-Chinese group members but indirect with Chinese peers, adjusting their style based on the group environment, stating they would "do the same" if everyone in the group expressed their opinions directly. This may explain the frequent use of explicit correction, as they interacted with people of equal status and similar cultural backgrounds, aligning with Yan's (2016) findings.

Interaction data reveal that participants used inclusive, tentative language or indirection by asking a question instead of direct statements to soften their PCF or negative comments (Excerpt 9). When giving explicit correction, they conveyed humility and uncertainty to reduce their authority and show politeness. This aligns with Carson and Nelson (1996), who found that Chinese learners were reluctant to claim authority, and Tian and Li (2018), who observed that they tried to avoid offending others when providing negative feedback.

Excerpt 9

1. P2 (11:35): fight的过去式好像是, fight的过去式不是加-ed吧? <The past tense of fight seems to be, the past tense of fight isn't plus -ed, is it?>=
2. P3 (19:59): 这里是不是应该是thought过去= < Shouldn't this be the 'thought' past tense>

3. P1(22:22): 有一个是except Woody好一些, all the toys except Woody<It's better to say except Woody, all the toys except Woody>=

CONCLUSION

The current study has explored two factors influencing Chinese learners' peer interaction and peer corrective feedback (PCF): perceived proficiency level and communication style. The analyses of group interaction show that mixed-proficiency groups used PCF most frequently and recast was the most frequent strategy. The focus-group interview data show that Chinese learners generally held a positive attitude toward receiving PCF but were cautious when providing it. These findings might be attributed to two issues. Firstly, subjectively perceived proficiency level may affect the provision and reception of PCF, as learners sometimes have difficulty understanding PCF and identifying others' mistakes. Therefore, perceived proficiency may result in reduced PCF episodes and/or hinder the reception and acceptance of PCF. Secondly, communication style can also influence learners' PCF. Participants generally agreed that they have an indirect communication style, leading them to avoid direct corrections. This was evidenced by the predominant use of implicit correction strategies, such as recast and indirection or inclusive language when providing explicit correction.

However, there are several limitations. Firstly, the small sample size limits the generalisability of the findings. The sample may not fully capture the diversity of Chinese learners, such as those studying in other English-speaking countries or domestic Chinese contexts. Secondly, the high-dominant groups included only one low-proficiency participant, which would have reduced the opportunities for low-proficiency learners to contribute to the discussion. Furthermore, the very narrow proficiency gap between participants (B1 to C1) might not adequately capture the dynamics of more varied proficiency pairings. Future studies could explore wider proficiency gaps (e.g., A2 to C1) to better understand how proficiency differences influence peer interaction and PCF. Thirdly, while low-proficiency learners provided valuable insights in the interviews, the lack of high-proficiency participants' perception may lead to an insufficient knowledge of PCF dynamics. Future studies should involve interviews with high-proficiency learners to explore whether and how their perceptions and practices of PCF differ from those of less proficient learners. Additionally, stimulated recall methodologies could be used to better understand factors influencing PCF practices. Participants could review recordings of their interactions and reflect on their decision-making processes

(e.g., why they chose explicit corrections over other types). Lastly, the communication styles of some participants might have been influenced by their extended residence in Australia. Future research could address this limitation by conducting longitudinal studies to examine whether prolonged exposure to Western communication norms influences the indirect communication style typically associated with Chinese learners.

The findings of this study provide insights into the grouping of students with varying language proficiency levels. Drawing from statistical data and post-task interviews exploring students' perceptions, the research suggests that to promote the effective use of PCF, it is advisable to form mixed-proficiency groups comprising learners of different levels. This allows lower-proficiency learners to benefit from interactions with their higher-proficiency peers. However, participants did not regularly engage in providing PCF, and their perceptions reflected a sense of caution or hesitation when providing PCF. The findings highlight the need to directly address the advantages of PCF with students and provide them with guidance on effectively offering feedback to their peers (Sippel & Jackson, 2015).

AUTHOR

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APPENDIX A

Group	Members	Task
Low proficiency 1	Zhen, Lan, Jia, Emma	1A
Low proficiency 2	Yun, Lan, Emma, Zhen	1B
Low proficiency 3	Yilin, Zichen, Guang	1A
Low proficiency 4	Yunqian, Zichen, Guang	1B
Low proficiency 5	Shuai, Han, Hanyue	1A
Mixed proficiency 1	Zi (HP), Jia, Lan, Jie (HP), Zhen	1B
Mixed proficiency 2	Ling, Fei (HP), Emma, Yun, Yi (HP)	1C
Mixed proficiency 3	Yunqian, Xi, Chen (HP), Wan (HP)	1A
Mixed proficiency 4	Ting, Yin, Lorelei (HP), Yu (HP)	1A
High dominant 1	Jia, Yi (HP), Zi (HP), Fei (HP), Jie (HP)	1C
High dominant 2	Yun, Yi (HP), Zi (HP), Fei (HP), Jie (HP)	1A
High dominant 3	Ting, Meng (HP), Sam (HP), Yiyun (HP)	1B

Notes: HP – high proficiency participant.

APPENDIX B INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

Task

1. Do you have group activities when you are learning English?
2. Do you like to work in a group with other students when learning English?
3. Which factor(s) have contributed to your engagement in each of the activities?

Proficiency

1. What do you think about your English level? What do you think of the people you worked with in the group activities?
 - a. Compared to your peers in your major?
 - b. Compared to your peers in China?
2. How do you feel while working with higher/lower-level learners?
 - a. Do you believe that group work should be done with learners from the same or different levels? Why?
3. Did you speak differently when you worked in a group with a higher level than you did when you worked in a group with a similar/lower level to yours? Why?
4. Do you worry when you work with higher level group members?

Communication Style

1. Could you please describe how different you feel between speaking Chinese and English?
2. Do you think you speak English differently when you are in China compared to when you are here?
3. Do you think Australian people talk differently from Chinese people?

4. Do you feel that you have a different style when speaking English?
 - a. If you feel you talk differently speaking your first and second language, which style do you prefer? Why?
5. In the group activity, when you encountered a point of view that you disagreed with, what would you do?
 - a. What factors do you think impact your actions?
 - b. If you would express your different views, how would you put it? Do you think you would do it the same way as when you speak your first language?
6. I found Chinese/Japanese people more indirect than Westerners. What do you think? Do you agree?

Peer Corrective Feedback

1. In the group activity, when you discover your peers' mistakes, what would you do?
 - a. Do you think there will be differences between when you speak your first language and when you speak English? Why?
2. Do you think you are happy when your peers correct your mistakes during group activity? Or do you feel offended?
3. Do you correct your peers? How do you do that?
4. Do you think English level may affect you when you correct others or when others correct you? Can you give me examples?
5. In your opinion, do Chinese students like to correct others? Do they like to be corrected?
6. How do you feel when you are corrected by someone who has a higher level than you? What about someone who has a lower level?
7. Do you understand when your peers correct you? Was there any time when you didn't understand your peers? How did you solve it?

8. Do you have any experience when you hurt other people's feelings when you correct them? Or when you are hurt when they correct you? Why do you think this happened?